

Problem Description

Imagine an application that receives the parameters as exemplified below:

```
java Application -timeout 3000 -file data.csv -verbose
```

In Java, the main() method receives a String array with the execution arguments:

```
public static void main (String[] args){...}
```

In the example, the args array would contain the following elements:

```
String[] args = {"-timeout", "3000", "-file", "data.csv",  
                "-verbose"};
```

To store this information and use it when necessary, the application usually creates a class whose attributes should receive this information. For example:

```
public class Parameters{  
  
    //should receive a number after -timeout  
    private long timeout;  
  
    //should receive a string after -file  
    private String filename;  
  
    //should be true if -verbose is present  
    private boolean verbose;  
  
    //getters and setters omitted  
}
```

To retrieve command-line parameters from an array and set into a class can be a non-trivial task. Additionally, there might also be other issues, such as mandatory parameters, parameter values validation and mapping values to custom classes.

Framework Description

The goal of the framework that is developed in the experiment is to map command-line parameters received by an application in the main() method to class attributes. This mapping is performed using annotations. The class Parameter would receive annotations as presented below:

```
public class Parameters {  
  
    @NumericValue(name="timeout")  
    private long timeout;  
  
    @TextValue(name="file")  
    private String filename;  
  
    @IsParameterPresent(name="verbose")  
    private boolean verbose;  
  
    //getters and setters omitted  
}
```

The framework execution should be invoked by using a single method invocation:

```
Parameters p = ParamMapper.map(args, Parameters.class);
```

Framework Internal Structure

In the internal structure, the framework implements the pattern Metadata Container. The source code below presents a template that is used by the framework:

```
public class ParamMapper {

    public <E> E map(String[] args, Class<E> paramClass){
        ParamMapperContainer c = readMetadata(paramClass);
        E paramInstance = (E) readParameters(args, c);
        return paramInstance;
    }

    private ParamMapperContainer readMetadata(
        Class<?> paramClass){
        //create an instance of ParamMapperContainer
        //add information based on the annotations
        //return it
    }

    private Object readParameters(String[] args,
        ParamMapperContainer c){
        //Create instance from the parameter class
        //Use metadata container to know what should be in
        //each class field.
        //add information based on the annotations
        //return it
    }
}
```

The method `map()` is the main method that invokes framework functionality. It should invoke `readMetadata()` to read the class metadata and annotations. This method returns an instance from the class `ParamMapperContainer`, which should contain all information needed about the target class (`paramClass`) for the framework to execute.

After that, the framework should execute the method `readParameters()` that receives the command-line parameters and the metadata container, which is an instance from the class `ParamMapperContainer`. It should create an instance of the target class (passed on the parameter “`paramClass`”) and set the parameters to its fields based on the metadata existing in the container. After that, this instance is returned.

Framework Annotations

The framework has implemented annotations that map parameters from the command line and map them to the fields of a class.

- `@IsParameterPresent(String name)` - This annotation is used to map boolean fields. If the string name is present in the command line, then the field annotated with `@IsParameterPresent` should receive true. If the element is annotated with `@IsParameterPresent` and the string name is not present in the command line, then the field annotated with `@IsParameterPresent` should receive false.
- `@TextValue(String name)` - This annotation is used to map String fields. If the string name is present in the command line, then the field annotated with `@TextValue` should receive the text following parameter name. For instance, consider the command “-A some text”, and the annotation `@TextValue(name = “A”)`, means that the String field annotated with `@TextValue` will receive “some text” as its value.
- `@ParameterFormat(String expression)` - This annotation specifies the format of the value received by a String field. For instance, consider the annotation `@ParameterFormat(expression="^[a-zA-Z]*$")`, means that the String field must receive a value containing only letters.
- `@ParameterLength(int min, int max)` - This annotation specifies the minimum and maximum length of a string field. For instance, consider the annotation `@ParameterLength(min=3,max=10)`, means that the field must receive a string value of a 3 characters minimum and at most 10 characters long.
- `@NumericValue(String name)` - This annotation is used to map numeric fields. If the string name is present in the command line, then the field annotated with `@NumericValue` should receive the text following parameter name. For instance, consider the command “-A 2”, and the annotation `@NumericValue(name = “A”)`, which means that the numeric field annotated with `@NumericValue` will receive 2 as its value.
- `@ParameterPrecision(int decimalPlaces)` - This annotation specifies the maximum of decimal places allowed to a floating point field. For instance, consider the annotation `@ParameterPrecision(decimalPlaces=2)`, which means that the floating point field annotated with `@ParameterPrecision` must have at most 2 decimal places (e.g 3.07).
- `@ParameterRange(int min, int max)` - This annotation specifies the minimum and maximum value allowed to a numeric field. For instance, consider the annotation `@ParameterRange(min = 3, max = 8)`, must have values within the interval [3,8].

- `@CompositeParameter` - This annotation specifies if the field is an instance of a Composite class. Consider the class `Person` as a composite class, since a `Person` has attributes like `String name`, `int age`, and so on.
- `@DateValue(String name, String format)` - This annotation is used to map Date fields, where the name parameter must be in the command line and its value must be in the specified format.
- `@Mandatory` - This annotation is used to determine if the field must be instantiated, that is it must be in the command line. Consider a numeric field annotated with `@NumericValue(name = "A")` and `@Mandatory`, then a valid command line must have the parameter "A", e.g "-A 2".